

Research Article

Pattern of Frontal and Default Activity in Older Adults Supports Memory

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Abstract

Though a matter of debate, prior neuroimaging work has shown that increased prefrontal activity can benefit cognitive performance under conditions where other brain regions show age-related decline; other evidence suggests that older adults exhibit deficits in suppressing default network activity during cognitive tasks relative to younger adults. This experiment examined the extent older adults engage increased frontal activity to make up for suppression deficits in the default network during successful encoding. In this investigation, younger and older adults studied pictures of outdoor scenes before then taking a recognition memory test (high confidence old, low confidence old, high confidence new, low confidence new). Behavioral results showed memory was equivalent for both younger and older adults. Neuroimaging results contrasting confidently remembered trials with the forgotten trials yielded activity in the prefrontal cortex that was most pronounced in older adults. Further, activity in several posterior default network regions showed reduced suppression in the older compared to the younger adults. Testing the idea that frontal regions might engage to counteract age-related changes in default regions during successful encoding, we observed positive correlations between regions of the frontal lobe and several default network sites. Further interrogation revealed that these correlations were evident only in the higher-performing older, but not the lower-performing older or younger adults. These data suggest that increased frontal recruitment might offset age-related changes in several regions of the default network in support of memory performance.

Keywords: Aging; Default network; Episodic memory; Frontal lobes; Recognition

Introduction

A common finding in the functional imaging literature is that older adults show increased prefrontal activity relative to younger adults on a broad variety of cognitive tasks [1-3]. Though a matter of debate, there is evidence that this additional activation is sometimes beneficial to performance [4,5], and that the additional frontal activation might offset age-related change in other brain regions. The evidence in support of the view that increased frontal activity might be adaptive comes from several sources: First, individual differences studies have linked bilateral activity in frontal sites with better performing older adults (Cabeza, [4]; though see Colcombe et al., [6]; Koen & Rugg, [7] for alternative views). Second, studies examining subsequent memory effects have found that older adults activate additional frontal cortex during successful episodic memory formation [8,9]. Third, a number of studies have directly correlated frontal activations associated with successful encoding with measures of behavioral performance in older adults [10], although some have found the effect to occur only in low performers [11,12]. Fourth, evidence from non-correlational imaging methods suggests increased cortical recruitment is cognitively beneficial in older adults [13]. Taken together, these converging lines of evidence suggest that increased prefrontal activity in older adults is sometimes a functionally adaptive phenomenon [1,14-17] that is part of a flexible deployment of cognitive resources in response to age-related changes in brain activity.

Although various standards have been used to make the claim of beneficial brain activity recruitment in older adults, we offer somewhat more stringent criteria for compensatory engagement that is in line with more recent work [1]. First, greater recruitment should be demonstrated in the older relative to the younger adults. Second, this increased frontal activity should be linked to age-related functional change in other brain regions (e.g., greater frontal activity counteracts changes in brain activity in other regions). Third, and perhaps most importantly, this relationship should be tied to successful behavioral performance or be evident in subsets of better performing individuals, such as high-performing older adults. Although these standards do not exclusively describe beneficial functional recruitment, they do establish more conservative criteria in line with recent work [1].

There are many studies that meet the first criteria, particularly in increased frontal recruitment [18] and a subset that meets the second criteria of linking frontal activity to age-related changes in other regions. Grady et al., [10] and Gutchess et al., [9] both showed evidence that decreased medial temporal activity was related to increased frontal recruitment. The third criterion, relating the greater activation to behavioral performance while simultaneously confirming the first two criteria, has been demonstrated, but less readily. Gutchess et al., [9], found additional prefrontal recruitment in older but not younger adults for successfully encoded items in a memory task. In addition, in two different memory reports, Duverne et al., [11] and Miller et al., [12] both showed that successful memory encoding was specifically related to heightened prefrontal activity, but, somewhat paradoxically, only for low-performing older adults. Because it only occurred in low

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performers, these researchers suggested that heightened prefrontal recruitment might be a harbinger or marker of incipient neural pathology as others have suggested [7,19]. In line with the influential Scaffolding Theory of Aging and Cognition (STAC) framework [14,16], increased frontal lobe activity may counteract a variety of age-related neural insults, including structural shrinkage, decreased white matter integrity, and decreased activation across other brain regions, etc. Guided by STAC, we investigated the extent frontal activity may be linked to another set of regions showing age-related changes: the default network.

The default network is a set of brain regions spanning frontal, medial temporal, and parietal areas more active when the brain is ostensibly at rest [20]. Activity of the default network is thought to represent internally focused processes [21], a variety of thinking processes that should generally be disengage when performing many externally focused mental operations [22], such as successful memory encoding [23]. Age-related change in function of the default network, however, has been reported in a number of forms: in low-frequency oscillations at rest [24] as well as during active memory tasks [25], in reduction of functional coordination between default regions [26], and as reduced suppression of default activity during various active cognitive tasks [11,27-29] including at encoding in memory tasks [11,12]. In the present study, we attempt to draw these two sets of findings (i.e., frontal and default network differences with age) more closely together by interrogating the relationship between frontal and default network changes in a sample of older and younger adults. Previous studies have reported some relations between these regions. For example, Miller et al., [12] demonstrated that reduced suppression of default activity in older adults was related to increased frontal activation, but only in low-performing older adults. Further, Stevens et al., [25] reported functional connectivity between inferior frontal and posterior parietal but only for forgotten trials. Here we attempt to examine the relationship between frontal and default regions during successful encoding and test the possibility that frontal regions might be engaged to counteract changes in the default network commonly observed with age in service of better memory performance.

In the present study, we investigate the relationship between increased frontal activity and default network activity and relate that to memory performance. Younger and older participants studied scenes in the scanner (e.g., encoding was conducted while participants were in the fMRI scanner). This scene memory task is ideally suited to relating cognitive performance to neural activations because memory performance is typically age invariant on this memory task [9]. We make three predictions in this experiment. First, we expect to see increased brain activity in frontal regions in the older relative to the younger adults. Second, we predict that older adults will exhibit deficits in suppressing default mode region activity compared to younger adults. Third, we predict the pattern of increased frontal activity concomitant with decreased default suppression will be associated with increased memory performance, especially in better performing older adults. Such a pattern would suggest that increased frontal activity in older adults can be functionally adaptive and associated with better memory performance.

Materials and Methods

Participants: A total of 42 younger adults (mean age: 22.1, SD 1.8) and 35 older adults (mean age: 66.7, SD 4.2) were recruited from the University of Illinois and surrounding community. All participants were right-handed and native English speakers. Participants

were screened for psychiatric and neurological disorders (e.g., stroke, epilepsy, multiple sclerosis, etc.), vascular disease, psychoactive and vaso-active medication use. No participant reported taking CNS-active medications. All participants had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. All participants gave their informed written consent. All subjects participated in two sessions conducted on separate days: an fMRI session and a neuropsychological testing session.

The neuropsychology session included the following speed of processing measures: the Dot-Matching task based on the WAIS-R Digit-Symbol task [30], Digit-Symbol Comparison, Letter-Number Sequencing, and Pattern-Matching [31]; the following span tasks: Forward and Backward Spatial Span [32]; and the following measures of crystallized intelligence: the WAIS-Comprehension from the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale—III [33], and the Boston Naming Test [34]. Participants were screened for dementia using the Mini-Mental State Exam (MMSE; Folstein et al., [35]) and were included if they attained a score of 26 or higher, as done before [36]. The age groups differed on measures of fluid intelligence and on their MMSE scores (Table 1). Education and a measure of crystallized intelligence, the WAIS-comprehension, was equivalent across age groups. This pattern of age-related fluid intelligence declines and crystallized intelligence preservations is consistent with samples reported in other aging studies [11] and typical of older adults [37].

Neuropsychological measures (Means and Standard Deviation)				
	Younger		Older	
	Means	SD	Means	SD
Education	14.53	1.92	15.60	2.93
Boston Naming	14.50	0.94	14.40	0.98
Dot Matching	16.48	2.87	9.49	3.10 *
Digit Symbol	73.67	10.29	55.86	7.59 *
Letter-Number Sequencing	14.88	3.05	10.49	2.17 *
Spatial Span Backward	9.60	1.62	7.37	1.50 *
Spatial Span Forward	10.55	2.03	8.11	1.57 *
Pattern Matching	42.81	5.63	27.20	6.54 *
WAIS Comprehension	21.29	3.90	20.09	5.10
MMSE	29.07	0.95	28.31	1.23 *

Table 1: Comparisons of the younger and older groups on education and neuropsychological measures are shown. For each measure, means and standard deviations are reported.

* Significant at $p < .05$

In order to assess patterns of activity associated with better performance for some analyses, we split the participants of both age groups into “higher” and “lower” performance groups. Performance groups were determined via a median split on their D-prime (d') scores, a measure of their behavioral performance at recognition [38]. Individual d' scores for each subject were calculated using the high-confidence hit rate and the high confidence false alarm rate. The performance split yielded a group of 21 young high-performers (HP; mean age: 21.5, SD 1.6) and 21 young low-performers (LP; mean age: 22.7, SD 1.9) as well as 17 older high-performers (mean age: 65.9, SD 4.2) and 18 older low-performers (mean age: 67.4, SD 4.2). There was significant age difference between the high- and low- performance groups in the young ($t(40) = 2.2, p = .03$); however, there was no age difference for the older adults ($t(33) = 1.1, p = .28$).

Stimuli: A total of 192 color pictures of outdoor scenes, half of which contained water (e.g., lakes, streams, ocean, etc.), were used in this investigation as used before [39]. To attain sufficiently high miss rate important for a subsequent memory analysis (e.g., hits minus misses), every picture presented at encoding had a recognition lure matched for similar features (See Figure 1 for an example of an encoded item and its matched recognition lure). Across participants, items serving as studied items and matched lures were counterbalanced. Scenes subtended a maximum viewing angle of approximately 8.8 degrees.

Figure 1: An example outdoor scene used at encoding and its matched recognition lure are depicted.

Experimental design: Participants were first trained on the encoding task to ensure task comprehension. Prior to scanning, participants were given earplugs, noise-dampening headphones, and a four-button response pad in their right hand. Participants were instructed to minimize all movement, especially head movement, throughout the entire fMRI session. Once placed in the MRI scanner, participants studied a total of 96 scenes during encoding. For each study phase trial, a single scene was presented for 4 seconds. For each scene, participants performed the incidental encoding task deciding, “Is there water in the scene?” We gave this encoding orienting task to ensure that participants were attending to stimuli as is common in memory experiments [40-49]. Each encoding trial was separated by a variable inter-trial interval of between 4 and 14 seconds. Responses were recorded with the index and middle fingers of the right hand.

An out-of-scanner recognition test was administered approximately 30 minutes after the encoding session ended. Participants were shown the 96 old studied scenes as well as the 96 novel matched lures. For each recognition trial participants were instructed to rate each scene as old with high confidence, old with low confidence, or as scene they have not previously seen (i.e., new with high confidence, new with low confidence). Participants made their recognition decision with the index, middle, ring and pinky fingers of their right hand.

fMRI scanning: All fMRI scanning took place on a Siemens (Erlangen, Germany) 3T Allegra head only system. High resolution T1-weighted structural Magnetization Prepared Rapid Gradient Echo (MPRAGE) structural scans were acquired in 160, 1.25 millimeter thick, slices aligned to the long axis of the hippocampus. Standard interleaved gradient echo-planar images (EPI; TR = 2000 ms, TE = 25 ms, flip angle = 80°, FoV = 240mm, matrix size = 64 x 64) were acquired in 32 slices (4mm thick, .4mm interslice gap) aligned to the AC-PC line using a single-channel head coil.

fMRI data analysis: All preprocessing steps and image analyses were implemented in MatLab (The Mathworks, Natick, MA). The following preprocessing steps were carried out on all the EPI images: The raw DICOM EPI images were converted into Nifti format, realigned to the first acquired image to remove movement artifacts,

corrected for slice acquisition sequence, temporally smoothed using a high pass filter of 120 seconds, normalized to a standardized MNI template, re-sliced into 3-mm³ isotropic voxels, and then smoothed using an 8-mm Full Width at Half Max (FWHM) Gaussian kernel.

Based on recognition performance for each subject, encoding trials were back-sorted into three Memory Trial types: High-Confidence Remembered (HC-Rem), Low-Confidence Remembered (LC-Rem), and Forgotten (Forg) trials (collapsing across confidence). HC-Rem items were those encoded items correctly recognized as old with high confidence; LC-Rem were those correctly recognized as old but with low confidence, and Forg trials were items judged as new that were in fact old. Separate regressors for these three trial types as well as nuisance regressors for motion were submitted to a General Linear Model (GLM). Trials were modeled by convolving each event with a canonical HRF function.

Whole brain effects. We first conducted a subsequent memory whole brain analysis across all subjects (collapsed across age) by contrasting the HC-Rem trials with the Forg trials to isolate regions important to memory formation during encoding. Because we were interested in only those regions strongly tied to memory performance the LC-Rem were not included. This whole brain, random-effects 1-sample analysis (t-test) focused on clusters of 10 or more voxels surviving a threshold of $p < 0.001$. Because our hypothesis focused on the relationship of frontal activation increases to default suppression deficits in older adults, we used the significant frontal areas from this analysis as regions of interest for later analyses. Our Frontal Regions of Interest (ROIs) were defined as all functionally active voxels surviving our statistical threshold. Because of the near ubiquitous finding of increased frontal recruitment of older compared to younger adults, we then examined age differences in these frontal ROIs by extracting and comparing the parameter estimates for the HC-Rem trials to verify that older adults activated more than the younger adults for the successfully encoded trials.

The next analysis step identified regions which showed an Age (younger, older) by Memory Type (HC-Rem, Forg) interaction. The analysis allowed us to focus on regions showing magnitude differences in the subsequent memory effect between the younger and older adults. The analysis resulted in several default regions. These default regions were then used to assess our main hypothesis: that age-related suppression deficits in the default network would correlate with heightened frontal activation. In the next step, we divided older and younger subjects into high and low performing groups to assess whether correlations between frontal and default regions differed as a function of performance group. As a final step, we then performed a Fisher's z-transformation on the frontal-default correlations to examine whether correlations significantly differed between the higher- and lower- performing older adults.

Results

Behavioral results

A corrected measure of recognition performance [38] was calculated for each participant using the high-confidence hit rate and the high-confidence false alarm rate to new items. The performance on the d' measure as well as the hit and false alarm rates is presented for the recognition task in table 2. A comparison of the d' recognition scores did not show any group differences, though there was a trend of a memory advantage of the younger adults ($t(75) = 1.85, p = 0.07$).

Behavioral Performance by Age												
	HC-Hits		LC-Hits		Missed		HC-FA		LC-FA		d' (Corrected Recognition)	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Younger	0.46	0.13	0.26	0.11	0.27	0.11	0.17	0.08	0.3	0.13	0.89	0.4
Older	0.55	0.11	0.16	0.1	0.27	0.1	0.28	0.13	0.2	0.12	0.74	0.23
Behavioral Performance by Age and Performance Group												
HP-Y	0.51	0.13	0.21	0.1	0.27	0.11	0.14	0.07	0.26	0.11	1.18	0.32
LP-Y	0.41	0.11	0.31	0.11	0.28	0.12	0.21	0.07	0.35	0.13	0.59	0.19
HP-O	0.56	0.13	0.17	0.1	0.25	0.11	0.23	0.11	0.22	0.12	0.93	0.18
LP-O	0.54	0.1	0.16	0.1	0.29	0.1	0.33	0.09	0.18	0.12	0.57	0.11

Table 2: Behavioral performance as indexed by the high and low confidence hit rate; the misses; the high and low confidence false alarm rate; and a measure of corrected recognition, d-prime; are shown for the younger and older adults, and then split across the performance groups. For each measure, Means (M) and Standard Deviations (SD) are reported. (HP-Y, Higher-performing young; LP-Y, Lower-performing young; HP-O, Higher-performing old; LP-O, Lower-performing old).

Although this trend implies some degree of memory difference between the older and younger adults, it should be noted that we used only the high confidence hits and high confidence false alarms to calculate d'. When we examined overall hits and false alarms (collapsing across confidence rating) to calculate d', the means for young and old were .68 and .64, respectively, a difference that did not approach significance (p = 0.52), suggesting that more traditional measures of hits and false alarms yield no age differences.

Recognition for the high- and low-performance groups are also presented in table 2. The high-performing younger adults had a higher d' score (d'=1.18) than the high-performing older adults (d'=0.93; t(36) = 2.91, p<0.01), and both the low-performing older (d'=0.57; t(37) = 7.5, p<0.01) and the low-performing younger groups (d'=0.59; t(40) = 7.3, p<0.01). There was no difference between the low-performing younger and older adults (t(37) = 0.34, p = 0.74). The high-performing older group had significantly better d' scores than the low-performing older group (t(33) = 7.1, p < 0.01). Within the older performance groups, the difference in corrected recognition was driven by more HC-FA trials in the low-performing older group than the high-performing group (t(33) = 2.7, p < 0.05). The older performance groups did not differ on either the HC-Rem (t(33) = 0.39, p = 0.70) or Forg trials (t(33) = .95, p = 0.35).

fMRI results

To isolate regions uniquely associated with memory, we first contrasted the HC-Rem with the Forg trials. Results from this analysis are presented in table 3A and figure 2. We found extensive activations in occipital and inferior temporal regions in both the left and right hemispheres¹. In addition, frontal activation emerged in the left and right posterior inferior frontal, left anterior inferior frontal, and left and right orbitofrontal cortex. An examination of the parameter estimates from the HC-Rem trials from these primary frontal regions of interest

¹The extensive activity from the HC-Rem minus Forg contrast, also yielded extensive medial temporal activity, including the parahippocampus. Although the parahippocampal activity is not the focus of this report, we note that bilateral regions of the parahippocampus showed age-related reductions consistent with previous reports of aging deficits in medial temporal activity [9,23] in both the left and right parahippocampus.

(Figure 3), yielded evidence of greater frontal activation in the older adults in the left posterior (t(75) = 2.35, p < 0.05) and left anterior inferior frontal gyri (t(75) = 2.97, p < 0.05) as well as the left orbitofrontal cortex (t(75) = 3.07, p < 0.05). In the two frontal regions that did not show significant effects, the right posterior inferior frontal and the right orbitofrontal cortex, the age difference was in the direction expected with the older adults showing more recruitment. Finding increased frontal activity in older adults relative to younger supports our first prediction.

Figure 2: Regions exhibiting subsequent memory effects for all participants collapsed across age are shown. This analysis resulted from the contrast of the high-confidence remembered trials (HC-Rem) with the forgotten trials (Forg). A wide set of regions were active including occipital, temporal (including bilateral parahippocampus), parietal, and frontal areas (including orbitofrontal and inferior frontal regions). Threshold p < 0.001, minimum 10 voxel clusters.

We next examined regions showing an Age (younger, older) by Memory type (HC-Rem, Forg) interaction across the whole brain. Results of this analysis are depicted in figure 4 and table 3B. This

Figure 3: The mean parameter estimates for the high-confidence remembered trials are shown for younger and older adults in the five frontal regions-of-interest. The younger adults are shown in green and the older adults are shown in gray. Frontal regions where the older adults exhibited greater recruitments compared to the younger adults ($p < 0.05$) are marked with an asterisk.

analysis yielded multiple regions of the brain primarily located in the default network. Further interrogation of the default network regions showed a pattern of significantly less suppression of default activity (Figure 5) in older compared to younger adults in the right angular gyrus ($t(75) = 1.98, p < 0.05$) and the left precuneus ($t(75) = 2.71, p < 0.05$) consistent with previous findings [12]. The two default ROIs which did not reach significance, the medial prefrontal, and the left angular gyrus, both were in the expected direction of decreased default suppression in the older relative to the younger adults. Finding a pattern of reduced suppression of several default regions in the older compared to the younger adults supports our second prediction.

PFC-DN Correlations Thus far evidence replicates the previously reported effects of increased frontal and reduced suppression of the default network in older adults during encoding. A critical question, then, is the extent enhanced prefrontal activity might counteract age-related changes in default activity of the older adults in support of memory performance. Previous work has pointed to an initial link between frontal and default activity [12]. To further examine this relationship, we correlated activity within the frontal ROIs depicted in figure 3 and table 3A with those of the default network regions isolated in figure 4 and table 3B. Because previous findings have implicated a relation between frontal and default activity, we chose to include all frontal and default ROIs, and not simply those that differed as a function of age in the ROI analysis.

If a failure to reduce activity in the default network in the older adults is counteracted by increased prefrontal activity, then a positive correlation should emerge between these regions. Testing this possibility, significant positive correlations between default network and frontal activity emerged across several regions in the older but not

Figure 4: Whole brain results of an Age (younger, older) by Memory Type (HC-Rem, Forg) interaction are shown. Multiple regions of the default network showed this interaction effect including the medial prefrontal, precuneus, and left and right angular gyri. Threshold $p < 0.001$, minimum 10 voxel clusters.

Figure 5: The mean parameter estimates for the high-confidence remembered trials are shown for younger and older adults in the default network regions-of-interest. The younger adults are shown in green and the older adults are shown in gray. Regions where the older adults showed less default suppression compared to the younger adults ($p < 0.05$) are marked with an asterisk.

the younger adults. Specifically, we found that the left orbitofrontal cortex correlated with the left angular and medial prefrontal default regions, as well as with the left precuneus. Similarly, the right orbitofrontal cortex correlated with the left angular and the medial prefrontal default areas (Table 4). Because this relationship surfaced only for the older adults, it could represent a general aging phenomenon and might not explicitly be related to better memory performance. To address this concern, we additionally examined these correlations across the higher- and lower-performing groups. If the frontal activations are functionally adaptive and aids memory performance in older adults, then the relationship between default and frontal sites should

Region	Hemisphere	Coordinate (mm)			BA	Cluster	z-score
		x	y	z			
A. Supergroup, Subsequent Memory Effects (HC-Rem - Forg Trials)							
Middle Occipital	R	36	-69	27	39	1663	6.92
Middle Occipital	R	42	-81	15	19		6.59
Inferior Temporal	R	51	-51	-15	37		6.57
Middle Occipital	L	-36	-87	18	19	1600	6.69
Inferior Temporal	L	-48	-54	-12	37		6.1
Inferior Occipital	L	-48	-75	-9	19		5.91
Precuneus	R	15	-51	12	30	88	5.32
Posterior Inferior Frontal	R	45	6	30	9	100	4.86
Orbitofrontal	R	33	36	-12	11	15	4.29
Posterior Inferior Frontal	L	-36	9	27	9	66	4.23
Anterior Inferior Frontal	L	-42	27	18	46	58	4.11
Anterior Inferior Frontal	L	-45	33	12	46		4.08
Orbitofrontal	L	-33	36	-9	47	14	4.02
Amygdala	L	-21	-6	-18	30	15	3.97
Calcarine	L	-6	-51	6	7	17	3.63
Superior Parietal	R	-24	-51	45	46	10	3.6
B. Age X Memory Type Interaction Effects							
Medial Prefrontal	R	3	51	9	10	571	4.55
Orbitofrontal	L	-12	48	-6	32		4.54
Orbitofrontal	R	6	51	-6	10		4.28
Anterior Prefrontal	L	-21	60	9	10	113	4.37
Anterior Prefrontal	L	-21	51	18	10		3.85
Middle Frontal	L	-27	57	18	10		3.57
Angular	R	57	-60	33	39	53	4.3
Angular	R	51	-66	39	39		3.71
Precuneus	L	-9	-54	30	31	134	4.23
Posterior Cingulate	L	-3	-42	24	23		4.02
Precuneus	L	0	-63	30	10		3.61
Superior Frontal	L	-21	36	42	8	31	4.14
Orbitofrontal	L	-33	54	-3	10	22	3.94
Middle Frontal	L	-30	39	9	10		3.37
Cerebellum	R	30	-39	-27		21	3.7
Angular	L	-39	-57	24	39	28	3.66
Angular	L	-51	-66	30	39		3.33
Angular	L	-57	-66	24	39		3.27

Table 3: Results from the whole brain analysis yielded regions that showed subsequent memory effects [HC-Rem - Forg trials] across all subjects (A). Results from the whole brain analysis yielded regions that exhibited an Age (younger, older) by Memory Type (HC-Rem, Forg) interaction (B). Regions were active at a threshold of $p < .001$, with a minimum cluster size of 10 voxels. Results are ordered by cluster from highest to lowest z-statistic.

be stronger in the higher- compared to the lower-performing older adults. Results of this analysis confirmed this functionally adaptive interpretation (Table 4 and Figure 6). The frontal-default correlations emerged only in the higher-performing older adults but not in the lower-performing older adults or either of the young performance groups, supporting our third prediction. These correlations were significant, or showed significance trends, in nearly all the orbitofrontal-default network regions interrogating in support of the compensation account.

As a final measure, we performed a Fisher’s z-transformation to test the difference between the correlations between the higher- and

lower-performing older adults. Results of this analysis suggested a significant difference between the correlation coefficients in several of the frontal-default regions assessed (Table 5). Importantly, correlations between the left orbitofrontal site and the medial prefrontal, left precuneus, and right angular default network sites significantly differed between the higher- and lower-performing older adults, corroborating the findings of the correlation analysis.

Discussion

In this investigation, we examined the extent increased frontal activation and reduced default suppression was associated with better

Regions	Younger	Older	LP Younger	HP Younger	LP Older	HP Older
Left Orbitofrontal-Left Angular	0.01	0.44 **	-0.06	0.08	0.17	0.59 *
Left Orbitofrontal-Medial Prefrontal	0.21	0.52 **	0.13	0.27	0.19	0.66 **
Left Orbitofrontal-Left Precuneus	0.11	0.33 †	0.17	0.07	0.02	0.56 *
Left Orbitofrontal-Right Angular	-0.05	0.22	-0.36	0.15	-0.27	0.45 †
Right Orbitofrontal-Left Angular	-0.12	0.36 *	-0.09	-0.07	0.14	0.47 †
Right Orbitofrontal-Medial Prefrontal	0.2	0.44 **	0.03	0.35	0.22	0.51 *
Right Orbitofrontal-Left Precuneus	0	0.28	-0.05	0.21	0.02	0.45 †
Right Orbitofrontal-Right Angular	0.05	0.18	-0.36	0.24	-0.43	0.45

Table 4: Correlations between orbitofrontal and default network regions of interest are depicted split by age and performance group for the high confidence recognized trials. (HP = higher-performing; LP = lower-performing).

* Correlations are significant at $p < .05$ (two-tailed), **Correlations are significant at $p < .01$, † Correlation trend at $p < .07$

Correlated Regions	Z statistic
Left Orbitofrontal-Left Angular	1.36
Left Orbitofrontal-Medial Prefrontal	1.62 *
Left Orbitofrontal-Left Precuneus	1.65 *
Left Orbitofrontal-Right Angular	2.05 *
Right Orbitofrontal-Left Angular	0.99
Right Orbitofrontal-Medial Prefrontal	0.91
Right Orbitofrontal-Left Precuneus	1.25
Right Orbitofrontal-Right Angular	2.54 *

Table 5: Results from a Fisher’s z-transformation assessed correlation differences between the higher- and lower-performing older adults in several frontal-default network sites. The frontal-default regions tested were those reported in Table 4 which included regions where higher-performing older adults showed significant frontal-default correlations.

* Correlations differ at significance of $p < .05$

Figure 6: Scatterplots showing the relationship between frontal and default network regions are shown for the higher- and lower-performing older adults. Each data point represents parameter estimates from a single participant for the denoted frontal and default regions. Regression lines and their corresponding correlation coefficient are shown for each plot. Significant correlations between frontal and default sites ($p < .05$, two-tailed) are marked with an asterisk.

memory performance in older adults (relative to the younger adults). We have three primary findings: First, older adults showed increased activation in a range of frontal regions during successful encoding compared to younger adults. Second, older adults showed reduced suppression of various default mode regions during successful encoding relative to the younger adults. Third, the pattern of frontal-default activity was evident only for the high-performing elderly, suggesting that increased frontal activity in the older adults was linked to improved memory performance. This pattern of results is consistent with some lines of work suggesting that frontal cortex can show an adaptive neural response counteracting a variety of age-related changes [1,3,4,8,17,50,51], and linked to improved performance.

Behavioral Effects. Although it is common to see performance differences across age [37], we found no difference in memory between the younger and older adults in the current experiment. As we have argued elsewhere, it is important that behavioral performance should be similar (e.g., not statistically different) between younger and older adults to truly understand differences in brain activity patterns supporting memory [52]. Without similar memory performance across age, it is possible that differences in brain activity might reflect differences in memory performance and not necessarily reflect aging processes. Our behavioral results showing similar memory performance gives us greater confidence that the brain activity patterns we found in this experiment reflect processes associated with the aging of memory. Finding ways to promote memory is an important scientific goal [45,47,53-77], and the results of this experiment add to that vast literature.

Frontal Areas Associated with Successful Encoding. As our first primary finding, the current experiment yielded evidence for increased frontal activation in the older adults during successful encoding relative to the younger adults. We found greater activation in the older adults in left inferior frontal regions as well as the left orbitofrontal cortex compared to younger adults. The enhanced inferior frontal recruitment was found in an area that is typically associated with successful memory formation [78,79] and is consistent with a wider body of evidence that commonly reports age-related frontal recruitment increases across a wide set of tasks [18]. It is also consistent with Gutches’s [9] finding that frontal regions exhibited enhanced recruitment associated with remembered items and that of Miller et al., [12] who reported greater activations in prefrontal regions for successfully encoded items.

The finding of increased orbitofrontal cortex activity with age has not been commonly reported, as this region is more typically associated with emotional memory [80]. There are, however, three reasons to expect contributions of this region to support successful encoding. First, regions of the orbitofrontal cortex are highly interconnected with the medial temporal lobe, [81] a crucial memory formation region, making this area a potential candidate for a role in encoding. Second, evidence has specifically tied these regions to successful encoding [82-85]. Third, and perhaps most important, is evidence that this region serves a role in the encoding of complex scenes [82], which, given the nature of the present stimuli (i.e., pictures of outdoor scenes) establishes an important role for this region in this task. These findings suggest that additional orbitofrontal recruitment with age may be specific to successful encoding of scenes. The fact that the other frontal regions we interrogated did not show a similar relationship with default regions (e.g., left anterior prefrontal cortex) bolsters this claim of a role for the orbitofrontal regions in successful scene encoding in older adults. Overall, the fact that multiple frontal regions were uniquely recruited for successfully encoded items indicates the frontal activations observed were adaptive for encoding in older adults. Understanding memory processes across the lifespan is an important pursuit [36,39,86-98] and this investigation adds to that goal.

Default Network Activity. The second primary finding used a direct comparison of high-confidence remembered and forgotten items and isolated regions that showed Age by Memory Type interactions. These areas included the medial prefrontal cortex, the precuneus, and both the left and right angular gyrus in lateral parietal cortex. All of these regions have previously been associated with the default network [21]. Of particular importance in the present dataset was the finding that activity in these regions was driven by greater deactivation in the younger adults rather than by greater activation in the older adults consistent with previous reports of less suppression of default activity with age across several tasks [28,29,99] including successful memory encoding [11,12]. Despite the reports of age-related change in numerous regions of the default network including posterior parietal and medial prefrontal, previous reports of age effects across different memory paradigms have frequently focused on the medial parietal regions including the precuneus and/or the posterior cingulate [11,12,27,100]. Here we report data suggesting default network change in a range of regions in older adults. Generally, default activity is not conducive to externally-focused cognitive task performance, and thus may reflect internally focused or other types of task-unrelated processes [101] rather than task appropriate processing.

Once isolated, these regions then became the focus of further analysis linking prefrontal activity with age-related change in default activity. We hypothesized, based on previous findings implicating functional changes in the default network [12], that reduced default suppression observed in the older adults might be counteracted by increased frontal activity in service of successful encoding. Such a relationship was observed for older but not younger adults. Further, analyses indicated that the effect was driven by the higher-performing elderly group, who, it should be noted, did not differ in age from the lower performing older group. The linkage of the default activity to areas associated with successful encoding, in this case orbitofrontal regions, suggests a functionally adaptive age-related response associated with better behavioral performance [102].

Our present finding is similar to the Miller et al., [12] finding which also reported a relationship between default activity and prefrontal recruitment, but it differs in several significant ways. First, the relationship we reported was primarily between orbitofrontal and default sites, whereas Miller et al., [12] reported a correlation between superior frontal and medial parietal regions. We believe that this difference in region reflects important differences in task demands between the two studies (scene encoding versus name-face encoding). Second, and perhaps even more important, Miller et al., [12] reported significant correlations for the low- but not high-performing older adults; whereas we report significant correlations only for the higher-performing adults. It may be the case, as Miller et al., [12] suggested, that this pattern of activity in lower-performing adults might be due to incipient pathology. In contrast, the present data suggests a relationship between frontal and default sites in a subset of better performing older adults and thus might be indicative of brain activity patterns associated with "successful aging." These findings are consistent with predictions of the STAC model [14,16] which suggests that some regions might show an adaptive response for age-related change in other regions. Undoubtedly, heightened frontal recruitment with age and its relationship to performance is a topic of considerable interest and debate. Here we add to this literature.

In closing, we found that age-related changes in brain activity in frontal and default activity were associated with better performing older adults. To understand more fully the reciprocal role of neural systems with age, many more large-scale studies are needed that simultaneously measure the magnitude of neuropathological insults (e.g., white matter integrity, volumetric shrinkage and cortical thickness) and functional activation on two or more tasks in large samples. With such studies, more definitive answers will undoubtedly emerge.

Author Statement

The author has no conflicts to declare. This work is dedicated to the memory of Denise Park, a giant in the field of cognitive aging.

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